

Deliverable D1.22

10th GDI quarterly implementation report

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1. Executive Summary

The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) is a deployment project co-funded by the Digital Europe programme. GDI's main objective is to realise the data infrastructure required by the 1+MG initiative to share high-quality genotypic and phenotypic data across borders, the 1+MG Virtual Cohort. Countries participating have committed to reach a concrete operational level before the end of the project (progressing across different phases: onboarding, deployment or operational), which will require them to fulfil technical and non-technical requirements.

In addition, the establishment of required technical capacity in each Node has been identified as a critical factor for the success of the project and the long-term sustainability of the data infrastructure and the initiative.

This document presents the results of the initial European Genomic Data Infrastructure monitoring activities laid out in D1.12¹ that are initially focussed on:

- **the deployment of the technical expertise** required to deploy and operate the European Genomic Data Infrastructure to share access to data across borders, building the technical capacity to run the infrastructure beyond the end of the project, and,
- **the evolution of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure Nodes.** GDI Nodes will transition across different phases in their journey to be fully operational and integrated into the European Genomic Data Infrastructure.
- **identifying capacity-building actions required to target onboarding.** We acknowledge the different access to skills and resources each GDI Node has which implies that GDI Nodes will evolve and reach operational readiness at different speeds. We will use the information collected from GDI Nodes to identify gaps and opportunities to build capacity across the nodes both at the technical level and not technical levels to accelerate the journey across the different phases. In this case, we will focus on the onboarding phase.

These monitoring processes and tools aim to support GDI Nodes in their journey by assessing their progress on a quarterly basis and providing them with useful guidance and recommendations to reach their individual and project objectives, summarised in the commitment to have **6 Nodes technically operational by 2024**. This will be extended to **15 Nodes by 2026** with three additional Nodes reaching deployment and six more Nodes reaching onboarding.

A summary of the information collected every quarter will be presented to the 1+MG Group (in addition to being shared with project participants) in order to gather the contributions and support of the 1+MG Group on the direction of travel and their assistance in removing any roadblocks that could be identified.

The information presented here corresponds to the status of the Nodes by M33.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/7576210#.ZEYoBuzMJqs>

The current scope and content of the quarterly report could be updated if there is a need to modify it to better support the countries in their commitments or to facilitate reaching the overall project's initiatives. For instance, monitoring of the volume of data available in the European Genome Dashboard or via the 1+MG infrastructure could be implemented in the near future.

GDI has built on and updated the the 1+MG Framework², which is a useful resource to build capacity and facilitate the dissemination of the 1+MG recommendation and guidelines coming from the project support the implementation (B1MG, GDI, GoE, EHDS,...). All of the relevant GDI deliverables to date have been added to the 1+MG Framework the organisation has been updated to better reflect the current body of work. Taken together with the B1MG outputs, this helps GDI members to navigate recommendations and understand how the different components work together and align with the EHDS.

² <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

Outcomes	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi-party authorisation and authentication system, and enable the application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	No

<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable the extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

The methods and processes to gather the monitoring information were established in D1.12³. In this report, we will present and analyse the data initially collected as part of the periodic reporting exercise.

4. Description of work accomplished

Project participants and GDI Nodes were asked to provide the monitoring information related to the deployment of the technical expertise and the self-evaluation of the Node status.

4.1 Monitoring of the technical expertise deployment - Q10 results

4.1.1 Deployment of technical expertise at the GDI Node Level - Q10

The data show that **73%** of the expected technical expertise to be in place on average during the duration of the project was deployed, however 23.6% of institutes did not report their FTE usage this quarter. All countries have started to use their allocated FTEs with particular countries (such as Belgium, Spain, Malta, and Romania) that may need targeted support. However, this is a marked improvement over past quarters, with Cyprus being removed from the “watch list” above, indicating that national capacity is improving.

Project participants have reported delays in recruitment and some of them are also reorganising the national activities, which is expected to still have an effect in the forthcoming reports while the technical experts get fully deployed across all GDI Nodes. Some Nodes have managed to progress their work in concert with other projects, thus have not been claiming against their GDI FTE usage. It is possible that these grants have ended, and thus FTE usage has increased. Some nodes have indicated that they will not be able to use all of their allocated FTEs, so alternative plans are being sorted out by coordination.

The continued development across all of the three pillars will support the Nodes in guiding on how best to deploy their technical expertise. However, further development in this area is still required. The coordination team met in August, 2024 to come up with a plan to support technical expertise deployment at the Nodes. Over the coming months, they will send the Nodes a survey on current and planned FTE usage for Node and project development and will follow up with 1:1 conversations, starting with the Operational goal Nodes and moving down from there. The Q1 2025 requirements freezing activities have also helped pinpoint where development is required, followed by some technical planning and Node alignment that happened in August, 2025. Following this, WP3 can guide these Nodes towards adding technical expertise in these areas. Additionally, other opportunities exist to leverage the existing funding for project support, including:

- Support additional countries in joining GDI

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/7576210#.ZEYoBuzMJqs>

- Using Operational-goal Node project support FTEs to "mentor" Deployment & Onboarding Nodes
- Increase involvement of Nodes in WP6 to build data management capacity across all Nodes to accelerate the flow of data in compliance with the 1+MG Framework
- Guidelines/processes to prepare primary use data for secondary use, data quality aspects
- Federated/Distributed analytics Governance
- Support an existing Node to hire a security expert to guide the overall project

Table 1 Deployment of technical expertise across GDI Nodes

		Technical expertise deployment Pillar II		Based on inputs from 76.2%
		By M33		
GDI Node	Operational Readiness (target)	Baseline FTEs	Actuals FTEs	Actuals / Baseline
Belgium	Operational	4.0	1.0	26%
Czech Republic	Operational	4.0	2.9	74%
Denmark	Operational	4.0	1.7	44%
Estonia	Operational	4.0	4.7	117%
Finland	Operational	4.0	5.8	145%
France	Operational	3.4	3.7	109%
Germany	Operational	4.0	1.6	40%
Italy	Operational	3.9	1.9	48%
Luxembourg	Operational	4.3	3.7	88%
Portugal	Operational	4.0	4.2	104%
Slovenia	Operational	4.0	1.9	46%
Spain	Operational	5.0	1.6	32%
Sweden	Operational	5.0	3.9	78%
The Netherlands	Operational	5.0	4.6	92%
Norway	Operational	4.0	2.2	55%
Bulgaria	Deployment	1.8	2.1	115%
Latvia	Deployment	2.0	1.7	84%
Lithuania	Deployment	2.0	1.0	48%

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Croatia	Onboarding	1.0	0.9	89%
Ireland	Onboarding	1.2	1.0	80%
Cyprus	Onboarding	0.9	0.5	56%
Hungary	Onboarding	0.9	0.4	50%
Malta	Onboarding	0.0	0.0	0%
Romania	Onboarding	0.5	0.1	31%
Total:		72.8	53.1	73.0%

4.2 Monitoring the evolution of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure Nodes - Q10 results

- The main purpose of the GDI Nodes Operational Readiness data gathering is to monitor the Nodes' journey and identify capacity-building actions that will help them meet their targets by the end of the project.
- The Nodes have defined their timeline for advancement along the defined path towards operational readiness as illustrated in D3.2. However, this deliverable received limited input from the Nodes. Indicative timelines have been established for countries that have not provided a new roadmap based on the original data given at the onset of the project. As technical deployment has proceeded, we have begun to receive requests to update the timelines to match the technical and administrative realities the Nodes are facing. Countries have been encouraged to update their timelines based on recent developments. During the March 2024 meeting, Nodes timelines for the fulfilment of the commitments established in the 1+MG Roadmap⁴ and the project was presented ([see annexe V](#)) as well as recommended actions to demonstrate the development of technical capacity, the coordinator will follow up with the Nodes to ensure follow-through.
- There are two different views provided from the collected data, detailed in the following sections: 4.2.1: The level of operational readiness and 4.2.2: the overall percentage of progress across all indicators.
- Further analysis of the overall progress has been provided to identify capacity-building and other actions required to support nodes to reach the onboarding stage and beyond, as indicated by the Node roadmap.

⁴<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/1million-genomes-initiative-new-roadmap-adopted-scale-and-sustainability-phase>

4.2.1 GDI Node Operational Readiness level - Q10 results

- The GDI Node Operational Readiness level shows the expected phase Nodes should have attained by the time that the data is collected: Onboarding, Deployment and Operational, and where the GDI Nodes see themselves (self-evaluation) at the time of providing the information.
- The Q10 progress was focused on building on the finalisation of the requirements for GDI, analysing the gaps, understanding the impacts on the Nodes, and starting to build guidance, which will continue into the next quarters. This development will help guide Node advancement as well as providing them with solid specifications to support their own technical and financial planning.
- At this point, 2 Nodes (Spain and Sweden) have attained the full Onboarding level. Slovenia, Norway, Finland and Portugal in meeting all of the technical indicators for Onboarding, with 6 Nodes now reaching that level. However, several nodes have indicated that the work following the feature finalisation clear enough guidance has now been provided for them to take their Node advancement work to the next stage.
- Italy, Lithuania, Spain, France, Ireland and Sweden are still the only Nodes completing all of the non-technical indicators (see Annexe I).
- 13 of the 15 Operational-goal Nodes have reported that they have now completed 80% or more of the combined technical and non-technical steps required to reach Onboarding, bringing them into a position to complete the steps in the next two quarters. The Nodes that have not (Czech Republic and Luxembourg) will be approached by WP5 to see what additional support is required.
- The Onboarding technical indicator with the lowest % completion is 1.6.1, "Have deployed and validated an instance or PoC or an upgraded version incorporating additional use cases". The feature finalisation should provide further guidance for the Nodes towards completing this.. Another barrier that remains is the resistance of some Nodes to deploying software that has not yet reached production-readiness. Coordination is working with these Nodes to view the attainment of production-ready software as a collective goal of the Operational Nodes.
- 96% of the Nodes filled in the quarterly monitoring form this quarter, with only Hungary, an Onboarding-goal Node not reporting, so the current numbers give a relatively clear picture of the current state of the Nodes.

Table 2 GDI Nodes Operational Readiness level by M33

GDI Node Operational Readiness	Start date Duration By Month	2022-11		Overall status:	
		48			
		33	2025-7		
Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Vanguard Node?	Expected Phase	Current Phase	Technical Phase
Operational	Belgium	Yes	Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Czech Republic		Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Denmark		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Operational	Estonia		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Operational	Finland	Yes	Operational	TBD	Onboarding
Operational	France		Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Germany		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Operational	Italy		Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Luxembourg	Yes	Operational	TBD	TBD
Operational	Portugal	Yes	Deployment	TBD	Onboarding
Operational	Slovenia		Onboarding	TBD	Onboarding
Operational	Spain	Yes	Deployment	Onboarding	Onboarding
Operational	Sweden	Yes	Deployment	Onboarding	Onboarding
Operational	The Netherlands	Yes	Deployment	TBD	TBD
Operational	Norway	Yes	Onboarding	TBD	Onboarding
Deployment	Bulgaria		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Deployment	Latvia		TBD	TBD	TBD
Deployment	Lithuania		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Croatia		Onboarding	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Ireland		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Cyprus		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Hungary		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Malta		TBD	TBD	TBD
Onboarding	Romania		TBD	TBD	TBD
	Phases (Metrics)		Plan	Actual	
	Onboarding		7	2	
	Deployment		8	0	
	Operational		2	0	
	TBD		3	18	

Note: The “Expected Phase” is based on the Node Roadmap provided in D3.2. For the countries that have not given an updated timeline, the default timeline provided during the planning phase has been used.

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4.2.2. GDI Node general progress indicator - Q10 results

The GDI Node general progress indicator view, provides us with a metric that looks at all the individual steps across all the phases of the GDI Node Operational Readiness and calculates an indicator of progress (%) based on how each individual question, regardless of its level, has been answered, assigning a score as follows:

- 1.0 if the step has been met,
- 0.5 if the step has been met partially or,
- 0.0 if not met or not reported

Table 3 GDI Node general progress indicator and comparison with previous quarter data

M33-Q10							
GDI Node Operational Readiness		Step Phase Type					
M30 Reporting Complete	Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes =1, Partially =0.5)	Previous Quarter	
						Change since previous quarter	
yes	Operational	Belgium	Deployment	TBD	32%	32%	0%
yes	Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment	TBD	29%	29%	0%
yes	Operational	Denmark	Onboarding	TBD	57%	53%	4%
yes	Operational	Estonia	Onboarding	TBD	35%	35%	0%
yes	Operational	Finland	Operational	TBD	49%	47%	1%
yes	Operational	France	Deployment	TBD	53%	53%	0%
yes	Operational	Germany	Onboarding	TBD	57%	49%	9%
yes	Operational	Italy	Deployment	TBD	40%	40%	0%
yes	Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	TBD	25%	25%	0%
yes	Operational	Portugal	Deployment	TBD	51%	50%	1%
yes	Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding	TBD	57%	49%	9%
yes	Operational	Spain	Deployment nboardi		49%	49%	0%
yes	Operational	Sweden	Deployment nboardi		51%	51%	0%
yes	Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	TBD	47%	38%	9%
yes	Operational	Norway	Onboarding	TBD	46%	43%	3%
yes	Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding	TBD	24%	22%	1%
yes	Deployment	Latvia	TBD	TBD	25%	22%	3%
yes	Deployment	Lithuania	TBD	TBD	37%	32%	4%
yes	Onboarding	Croatia	Onboarding	TBD	12%	13%	-1%
yes	Onboarding	Ireland	TBD	TBD	19%	19%	0%
yes	Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD	TBD	18%	12%	6%
no	Onboarding	Hungary	TBD	TBD	25%	25%	0%
yes	Onboarding	Malta	TBD	TBD	18%	15%	3%
yes	Onboarding	Romania	TBD	TBD	10%	9%	1%
96%					36.09%		2%

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For a breakdown of progress within the Onboarding indicators, see Annexe I. Progress within the Operational-goal Nodes has been particularly slow this quarter, however many of the developers have been focused on completing the European-level. The requirements setting activities that are ongoing now will be another major boost in the coming quarters. Many Nodes have expressed that it is difficult to convince their management to deploy software before all of the requirements have been finalised, so these requirements-setting actions should support deployment for Nodes with these challenges. Finally, hiring remains a challenge, particularly for Deployment and Onboarding-goal Nodes, and, well-aligned with the levels of technical expertise deployment seen in Table 1, several countries have noted that further advancements can be made once local experts have been hired and this activity remains ongoing.

4.2.3. GDI Node general progress indicator - Capacity building actions

At this point in the project, ten Nodes have planned to achieve a stage beyond Onboarding, however most Nodes are still working through the Onboarding indicators, so support for advancement is focussed on these indicators. Further, while support is required for indicators in the Deployment level, we expect to gain more insight into this as the Nodes begin to tackle these indicators. An initial view on the required support should be available after the October Pillar II meeting in Paris. We are starting to see substantial progress already, with Germany, Slovenia, and The Netherlands increasing their overall indicator completion by 9% each last quarter alone.

In the "Onboarding" section, all indicators are at greater than 50% overall completion. Because of this, the indicators examined below focus on those below 90% completion by Operational-goal Nodes with the idea that these Nodes can guide the less mature Nodes in the coming year. Looking at the information provided by the Nodes, clear actions emerge to build capacity both across Technical and non-technical requirements (see [Annexe II](#)). For the calculation, a "yes" answer is considered 100% complete, a "no" is 0% and "partially" is 50% for each country:

- Onboarding steps with **0-50% completion** across **Operational-goal Nodes**
 - **N/A**
- Onboarding steps with **51-75% completion** across **Operational-goal Nodes**
 - **Have developed a national genomic plan or similar that secures long-term funding that matches the target implementation level.**
 - **Action:** A workshop took place in November 2024, coordinated by ISCIII, about the successful strategies of countries who have put a national genomic plan in place. The outputs and videos from this event were shared on the Framework and will be linked to from the operational readiness reporting spreadsheet. Furthermore, there is extensive planning underway to support Node development in this area, coordinated by ISCIII. Overall, the challenges here exist within national politics and economic considerations. The project will continue to produce high quality communications material to help the countries make their case to their ministries and politicians.

- Onboarding steps with 76-90% completion across Operational-goal Nodes
 - **API use cases considered, specifications drafted and implementation in progress**
 - **Decision on services and components utilised**
 - **Have deployed and validated an instance or PoC or an upgraded version incorporating additional use cases**
 - All three of the above indicators, while mostly completed across the Operational-goal nodes, face a combination of the same three challenges: 1) some Nodes were waiting on further steps after the feature finalisation that was only completed in September this year; 2) some Nodes were facing a mismatch between the designated GDI node and the organisation that will operate the infrastructure, leading to delays in development; and 3) sometimes related to #2, some nodes continue to face delays in recruitment of a suitable developer. Issue #1 should be mainly resolved and the Nodes should be able to get the next phase of work underway, even as details continue to be refined by Pillar II activities. Pillar II has collected information on which nodes are facing an organisational development vs operational mismatch so we can be aware of how this issue may impact future Node maturity work.
 - **Security mitigation, management, and reporting system being drafted.**
 - **Action:** Most Nodes indicate that this work is underway and the information they require is available. A FitSM workshop was held last quarter to help guide Nodes in this process. A spreadsheet is available to help support them in this work. We expect to see progress in the next two quarters.
- Deployment steps
 - Many of the Nodes should have made significant progress in these by this point. While there are still gaps that remain for the Operational-goal Nodes within Onboarding, coordination and WP3 needs to generally pressure and support Nodes into making progress into further steps. National capacity and upgrading the infrastructure to meet operational needs seem to be key gaps in this area. Nodes have clearly stated that they expect to see exponential progress in the coming quarters after the completion of the project feature finalisation.

5. Results

- Use of resources has improved this quarter. However, there are still a number of Operational-goal Nodes who need to be contributing towards the European level infrastructure. WP3, with the support of Coordination, will be addressing this in the coming quarter.
- Within the Nodes that were expected to have already reached the Onboarding stage, there are three, interrelated technical indicators, the drafting of a security mitigation plan, and the completion of a National Genomic Plan. The feature finalisation should provide sufficient guidance on this work and completion will help Nodes meet the technical indicators. The national genomic plan workshop should help with the latter, but it is ultimately up to the

governments to meet this requirement. Additional mitigation measures will be identified during the Pillar II face to face meeting in October.

- Additional capacity-building actions have been identified.

6. Discussion

The lack of a defined final feature set had been a major hurdle for deployment. Now that this has been set and the information is available to all within the project, the coordination team believes that the Nodes will be able to make significant progress in the coming months. Emphasising the plan for 6 continuous months of operation before the end of the project may be required to push the Nodes into completing their technical deployment steps.

7. Conclusions & Impact

Use of resources has improved, but it has not come with seeing contribution to the European-level infrastructure from some key Operational-goal Nodes. WP4 is working with Coordination to push these Nodes into action.

Identified technical capacity-building actions (section [4.2.3](#)) have been outlined, but a concrete plan needs to be put in place to support these when MS8 development work is completed.

8. Next steps

The next gathering of information from Nodes will take place in August, 2025.

Annex I. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Onboarding Summary

M33-Q10								
GDI Node Operational Readiness		Step Phase Type						
M30 Reporting Complete	Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes =1, Partially =0.5)	Onboarding Overall Progress	Onboarding Tech Progress	Onboarding NonTech Progress
yes	Operational	Belgium	Deployment	TBD	32%	85%	86%	83%
yes	Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment	TBD	29%	70%	64%	83%
yes	Operational	Denmark	Onboarding	TBD	57%	95%	93%	100%
yes	Operational	Estonia	Onboarding	TBD	35%	80%	93%	50%
yes	Operational	Finland	Operational	TBD	49%	95%	100%	83%
yes	Operational	France	Deployment	TBD	53%	95%	93%	100%
yes	Operational	Germany	Onboarding	TBD	57%	90%	93%	83%
yes	Operational	Italy	Deployment	TBD	40%	90%	86%	100%
yes	Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	TBD	25%	70%	64%	83%
yes	Operational	Portugal	Deployment	TBD	51%	95%	100%	83%
yes	Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding	TBD	57%	95%	100%	83%
yes	Operational	Spain	Deployment nboardi		49%	100%	100%	100%
yes	Operational	Sweden	Deployment nboardi		51%	100%	100%	100%
yes	Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	TBD	47%	80%	93%	50%
yes	Operational	Norway	Onboarding	TBD	46%	90%	100%	67%
yes	Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding	TBD	24%	70%	71%	67%
yes	Deployment	Latvia	TBD	TBD	25%	75%	71%	83%
yes	Deployment	Lithuania	TBD	TBD	37%	75%	64%	100%
yes	Onboarding	Croatia	Onboarding	TBD	12%	40%	50%	17%
yes	Onboarding	Ireland	TBD	TBD	19%	65%	50%	100%
yes	Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD	TBD	18%	40%	50%	17%
no	Onboarding	Hungary	TBD	TBD	25%	60%	50%	83%
yes	Onboarding	Malta	TBD	TBD	18%	60%	57%	67%
yes	Onboarding	Romania	TBD	TBD	10%	35%	29%	50%
96%					36.09%	83%	84%	81%

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Annex II. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Onboarding

M33-Q10										1.1.1	1.1.2	1.1.3	1.1.4	1.2.1	1.2.2	1.3.1	1.5.1	1.6.1	1.7.1
M30 Reporting Complete	Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes = 1, Partially = 0.5)	Onboarding Overall Progress	Onboarding Tech Progress	Onboarding NonTech Progress	Step Phase Type	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding	Onboarding
										Technical	Non Technical	Non Technical	Non Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical
										API use cases considered, specifications drafted and implementation in progress	Have started to build national capacity (ELSI, data quality, technical infrastructure functions) for the deployment of the 1+MG node and to support data flow.	Have developed the 1+MG NMG or equivalent structure to contribute to the 1+MG Initiative.	Have developed a national genomic plan or similar that secures long-term funding that matches the target implementation level.	Decision on services and components utilised	Software development best practises identified and implemented at the node	Security mitigation, management, and reporting system being drafted.	Have deployed or made available the initial physical infrastructure for the evaluation of the current PoC, or an upgraded version incorporating additional use cases.	Have deployed and validated an instance or PoC or an upgraded version incorporating additional use cases	Load of synthetic data, functionalities demonstrated in development environment
yes	Operational	Belgium	Deployment	TBD	32%	85%	86%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
yes	Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment	TBD	29%	70%	64%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	No
yes	Operational	Denmark	Onboarding	TBD	57%	95%	93%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	Estonia	Onboarding	TBD	35%	80%	93%	50%	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	Finland	Operational	TBD	49%	95%	100%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	France	Deployment	TBD	53%	95%	93%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	Germany	Onboarding	TBD	57%	90%	93%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
yes	Operational	Italy	Deployment	TBD	40%	90%	86%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
yes	Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	TBD	25%	70%	64%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes
yes	Operational	Portugal	Deployment	TBD	51%	95%	100%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding	TBD	57%	95%	100%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	Spain	Deployment nboardi		49%	100%	100%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	Sweden	Deployment nboardi		51%	100%	100%	100%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	TBD	47%	80%	93%	50%	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
yes	Operational	Norway	Onboarding	TBD	46%	90%	100%	67%	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
yes	Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding	TBD	24%	70%	71%	67%	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	No
yes	Deployment	Latvia	TBD	TBD	25%	75%	71%	83%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially
yes	Deployment	Lithuania	TBD	TBD	37%	75%	64%	100%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially
yes	Onboarding	Croatia	Onboarding	TBD	12%	40%	50%	17%	Yes	No	Partially	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Partially	Partially
yes	Onboarding	Ireland	TBD	TBD	19%	65%	50%	100%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially
yes	Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD	TBD	18%	40%	50%	17%	Partially	Partially	No	No	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	No	No
no	Onboarding	Hungary	TBD	TBD	25%	60%	50%	83%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially
yes	Onboarding	Malta	TBD	TBD	18%	60%	57%	67%	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially
yes	Onboarding	Romania	TBD	TBD	10%	35%	29%	50%	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	No
96%					36.09%	83%	84%	81%											
									overall yes	63%	71%	83%	29%	71%	63%	54%	75%	42%	58%
									overall no	0%	4%	4%	17%	0%	8%	8%	4%	4%	17%
									overall partial	38%	25%	13%	54%	29%	29%	38%	21%	54%	26%
									total completion	81%	83%	90%	56%	85%	77%	73%	86%	69%	71%

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Annex III. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Deployment

M33-Q10							2.1.1	2.1.2	2.2.1	2.2.2	2.3.1	2.3.2	2.4.1	2.4.2	2.5.1	2.6.1	2.7.1	2.8.1	2.9.1	
M30 Reporting Complete	Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node Operational Readiness			Step Phase Type			Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	Deployment	
		GDI Node	Expected Phase	Current Phase	Progress indicator: (Yes =1, Partially =0.5)	Deployment Tech Progress	Deployment Non Tech Progress	Non Technical	Non Technical	Technical	Non Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical
							Storage and network capacity needs achieved ad hoc by hosting institution	Common software development best practices employed	Minimal set of APIs for the five functionalities	Non Technical Have built national capacity (ELSI, data standards, technical infrastructure functions) for the deployment of the 1+MG node and to support data flow	Network and storage meets reliability, robustness, performance, security, and capacity requirements	Deployment of 1+MG national node for connection to the staging environment with synthetic data loaded	Compliance and stress tests drafted and refined in context of requirements	Implementation & successful performance of compliance and stress tests of node in isolation	Have completed the initial data load of synthetic data and linking to staging version of 1+MG European Infrastructure	Deployment of 1+MG national node but it is not yet connected to the 1+MG Infrastructure	Communication established with user portal and 1+MG Infrastructure	Have finalised the initial deployment of national 1+MG production node enabling data access across borders in a staging environment	Production version ready to be deployed into production within the wider GDI	
yes	Operational	Belgium	Deployment	TBD	32%	6%	50%	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment	TBD	29%	6%	63%	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No						
yes	Operational	Denmark	Onboarding	TBD	57%	22%	100%	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Estonia	Onboarding	TBD	35%	17%	63%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Finland	Operational	TBD	49%	44%	75%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Yes	No	No	No
yes	Operational	France	Deployment	TBD	53%	33%	100%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially		Partially				
yes	Operational	Germany	Onboarding	TBD	57%	56%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially
yes	Operational	Italy	Deployment	TBD	40%	17%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	TBD	25%	11%	13%	Partially	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	Partially	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Portugal	Deployment	TBD	51%	61%	63%	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	No	No
yes	Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding	TBD	57%	78%	75%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	No
yes	Operational	Spain	Deployment nboardi		49%	39%	75%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No
yes	Operational	Sweden	Deployment nboardi		51%	44%	88%	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No
yes	Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	TBD	47%	44%	88%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Partially	No	Yes	Partially	No
yes	Operational	Norway	Onboarding	TBD	46%	44%	63%	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No
yes	Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding	TBD	24%	0%	25%	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Deployment	Latvia	TBD	TBD	25%	0%	25%	Partially	No	No	No	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Deployment	Lithuania	TBD	TBD	37%	28%	63%	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Onboarding	Croatia	Onboarding	TBD	12%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Onboarding	Ireland	TBD	TBD	19%	0%	0%						No							
yes	Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD	TBD	18%	0%	50%	Partially	Partially		Partially	Partially	No							
no	Onboarding	Hungary	TBD	TBD	25%	6%	50%	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Onboarding	Malta	TBD	TBD	18%	0%	0%						No							
yes	Onboarding	Romania	TBD	TBD	10%	0%	0%													
96%					36.09%	28%	59%													
					overall yes			54%	46%	29%	8%	17%	33%	4%	0%	13%	8%	13%	0%	0%
					overall no			17%	26%	33%	29%	29%	54%	46%	79%	63%	63%	67%	83%	95%
					overall partial			29%	28%	38%	83%	54%	13%	50%	21%	25%	29%	21%	17%	4%
					total completion			66%	60%	48%	40%	44%	40%	29%	10%	26%	23%	23%	8%	2%

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Annex IV. GDI Node general progress indicator table - Operational

M33-Q10							3.1.1	3.2.1	3.3.1	3.4.1	3.5.1	3.6.1	3.7.1	3.8.1	3.9.1	3.??	3.??		
M30 Reporting Complete	Operational Phase (2026)	GDI Node	Expected Phase	Current Phase	Step Phase Type	Progress indicator: (Yes = 1, Partially = 0.5)	Operational Tech Progress	Operational Non Tech Progress	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	Operational	
									Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Technical	Non Technical	Non Technical
									Periodic review of security of existing infrastructure to make sure it complies with current best practice	APIs assessed against users needs and feedback, updates scheduled	Periodic auditing and revision of network and storage capacity to ensure stakeholders needs are met	Compliance and stress tests regularly reviewed to ensure correspond to updated requirements and use cases	Deployment of national 1+MG Infrastructure node (production) enabling data access across borders when agreement allowing it are in place	Continuous support to Node interoperability, development, and security	Continuous 1+MG infrastructure developments to meet use cases needs	Evaluate and support technical solutions tested and proposed by pillar III based on explicit use cases requirements	Node meets technical KPIs	Continuous Capacity building at European level	Continuous support to EU users via node helpdesk (ELSI, data quality, data standards, technical infrastructure functions)
yes	Operational	Belgium	Deployment	TBD		32%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Czech Republic	Deployment	TBD		29%	0%	0%											
yes	Operational	Denmark	Onboarding	TBD		57%	39%	25%	Yes	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	Partially	No	No	No	No	Partially
yes	Operational	Estonia	Onboarding	TBD		35%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Finland	Operational	TBD		49%	0%	0%											
yes	Operational	France	Deployment	TBD		53%	11%	25%	Partially		Partially								Partially
yes	Operational	Germany	Onboarding	TBD		57%	28%	0%	Partially	Partially			Partially	Partially	Partially				
yes	Operational	Italy	Deployment	TBD		40%	0%	0%											
yes	Operational	Luxembourg	Operational	TBD		25%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Portugal	Deployment	TBD		51%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Slovenia	Onboarding	TBD		57%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Spain	Deployment nboardi			49%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	Sweden	Deployment nboardi			51%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Operational	The Netherlands	Deployment	TBD		47%	0%	25%											Partially
yes	Operational	Norway	Onboarding	TBD		46%	0%	0%											
yes	Deployment	Bulgaria	Onboarding	TBD		24%	0%	0%											
yes	Deployment	Latvia	TBD	TBD		25%	0%	0%											
yes	Deployment	Lithuania	TBD	TBD		37%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Onboarding	Croatia	Onboarding	TBD		12%	0%	0%	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
yes	Onboarding	Ireland	TBD	TBD		19%	0%	0%											
yes	Onboarding	Cyprus	TBD	TBD		18%	0%	0%											
no	Onboarding	Hungary	TBD	TBD		25%	0%	0%											
yes	Onboarding	Malta	TBD	TBD		18%	0%	0%											
yes	Onboarding	Romania	TBD	TBD		10%	0%	0%											
96%						36.09%	4%	4%											
								overall yes	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
								overall no	88%	92%	92%	96%	92%	92%	96%	100%	100%	100%	88%
								overall partial	8%	8%	8%	4%	8%	8%	4%	0%	0%	0%	13%
								total completion	8%	4%	4%	2%	4%	4%	2%	0%	0%	0%	8%

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Annex V. Timelines for implementation according to target phase as

Onboarding: Croatia, Cyprus, Hungary, Ireland, Malta, Romania <i>Addressing national challenges for deployment</i>	Support
Involvement in 1+MG initiative (2024-Q4): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MS representatives participate in 1+MG MS meetings and Pillar I (GDI) - National experts are named and participate on the 1+MG WGs meetings (National implementation, ELIS, Sequencing, Standards, Infrastructure, Healthcare implementation, Health economics, Rare Diseases, Cancer, Common and complex (icl. Population genomics and Pharmacogenomics, infectious diseases) 	EC & Project coordination
Establishment of National Mirror groups (2025-Q2) National mirror group is in place (replicating 1+MG WG structure) and have regular meeting (e.g quarterly) to drive national implementation and adoption of 1+MG Roadmap and 1+MG Framework	EC & Project coordination
National genomic plan or equivalent (2026-Q4) Secure multi year funding to support the national operations of the 1+MG infrastructure (=> Workshop being planned for 24/4/2024 registration to be open)	EC & Project coordination
Deployment of GDI products in test environment (2025-Q4) Deployment of synthetic data and starter kit products on test environment (first release on 2023-Q3) and connected to test services (e.g. Test Beacon Network)	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination

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Deployment (in addition to Onboarding): Bulgaria, Latvia, Lithuania <i>Operational at the national level, not connected to EU operations</i>	Support
Deployment of GDI products in test environment (2024-Q4) Deployment of synthetic data and starter kit products on test environment (first release on <u>2023-Q3</u>) and connected to test services (e.g. Test Beacon Network)	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
Deployment of GDI products or interoperable solutions in pre-production environment (2025-Q3) Decision has been made on products that would be part of the national node and they are deployed in pre-production environment to join countries that has implemented Milestone 7 Data access governance demonstrator	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
National GDI node up up running in production environment providing services to the national community (2026-Q2) Deployment node realised	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination

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Operations (in addition to Deployment): Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands, Norway <i>Fully deployed national node Interconnected to EU services, able to provide access to data across borders following 1+MG Governance</i>	Support
Deployment of GDI products in test environment (2024-Q2) Deployment of synthetic data and starter kit products on test environment (first release on <u>2023-Q3</u>)	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
Deployment of GDI products or interoperable solutions in pre-production environment (2024-Q4) Decision has been made on products that would be part of the national node and they are deployed in pre-production environment to join countries that has implemented Milestone 7 Data access governance demonstrator	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
National GDI node up up running in production environment providing services to the national community (2025-Q3) Deployment node realised	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination
National GDI node connected to EU level services and providing across border access (2026-Q2) Operational node realised	Pillar II WP3 & WP5 Project coordination

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Annex VI. Visual progress of the Node Advancement

Technical Indicators.

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M33-Q10			Technical progress														
Node Goal & Level			Onboarding					Deployment					Operational				
Readiness			Onboarding					Deployment					Operational				
Node	Target	Current Level	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%
Belgium	Operational	TBD															
Czech Republic	Operational	TBD															
Denmark	Operational	TBD															
Estonia	Operational	TBD															
Finland	Operational	TBD															
France	Operational	TBD															
Germany	Operational	TBD															
Italy	Operational	TBD															
Luxembourg	Operational	TBD															
Portugal	Operational	TBD															
Slovenia	Operational	TBD															
Spain	Operational	Onboarding															
Sweden	Operational	Onboarding															
The Netherlands	Operational	TBD															
Norway	Operational	TBD															
Bulgaria	Deployment	TBD															
Latvia	Deployment	TBD															
Lithuania	Deployment	TBD															
Croatia	Onboarding	TBD															
Ireland	Onboarding	TBD															
Cyprus	Onboarding	TBD															
Hungary	Onboarding	TBD															
Malta	Onboarding	TBD															
Romania	Onboarding	TBD															

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Non-Technical Indicators

M33-Q10			Non-Technical progress														
Node Goal & Level			Onboarding					Deployment					Operational				
Node	Target	Current Level	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%	1-25%	26-50%	51-75%	76-99%	100%
Belgium	Operational	TBD															
Czech Republic	Operational	TBD															
Denmark	Operational	TBD															
Estonia	Operational	TBD															
Finland	Operational	TBD															
France	Operational	TBD															
Germany	Operational	TBD															
Italy	Operational	TBD															
Luxembourg	Operational	TBD															
Portugal	Operational	TBD															
Slovenia	Operational	TBD															
Spain	Operational	Onboarding															
Sweden	Operational	Onboarding															
The Netherlands	Operational	TBD															
Norway	Operational	TBD															
Bulgaria	Deployment	TBD															
Latvia	Deployment	TBD															
Lithuania	Deployment	TBD															
Croatia	Onboarding	TBD															
Ireland	Onboarding	TBD															
Cyprus	Onboarding	TBD															
Hungary	Onboarding	TBD															
Malta	Onboarding	TBD															
Romania	Onboarding	TBD															

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